

Supplementary Information

Supplementary Figure S1. Somatic Variant Calling Pipeline. From fastq reads to final variant calls. This pipeline is to be performed on each sample and encompasses essential steps, including three quality control cycles. Corresponding scripts are available in <https://github.com/montana-knight/Calling-Induced-Variants-with-RNA-Seq-Data>. The top yellow block corresponds to fastq data processing. The middle purple block covers read mapping and alignment file processing for the variant caller. The pink section represents the variant calling to tag and later filter out the likely inherited mutations. Finally, the bottom green block represents calling the variants and all associated filtration steps. The final output is a variant call file that can be further analyzed. Created with BioRender.com.

Supplementary Figure S2. Another approach for deduplication. Our unique deduplication approach minimizes the number of true biological duplicates being filtered out. Instead of deduplicating before variant calling, our pipeline saves deduplication until after the variant calling. (Left) Suppose a variant is called (T) and is only supported by identical reads which are mapped to the same location. Then, it would be considered the result of PCR amplification and filtered out. (Right) In contrast, if a variant is called (T) and is supported by more than one read (not identical in composition/mapped location), then it is not considered a PCR artifact and is retained for the next filtering step.